

Reservation and Social Justice

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Abstract

The reservation system in India, initially established to empower marginalized communities, has evolved into a complex and contentious issue. This paper examines the historical background and evolution of reservation policies from pre-independence to the present day. It explores the constitutional provisions governing reservation, including amendments and extensions, and analyzes the objectives and outcomes of the reservation system. Furthermore, it discusses the need for reevaluation and reform of reservation policies in light of contemporary social, economic, and political realities. Suggestions for reform include gradually reducing reservation quotas, diversifying criteria beyond caste, limiting reservations to initial stages rather than promotions, and fostering political consensus for reform implementation. The paper emphasizes the importance of balancing social justice objectives with the maintenance of standards in education, governance, and societal well-being. It concludes with a call for a rational and inclusive approach to reservation policies that prioritizes equality of opportunity while ensuring the sustainable development of Indian society.

Keywords Reservation, Social, Justice.

Introduction

Reservation as of today is seen as a system by which people are provided certain benefits by which particular section of society get enrolled in some good courses to study and further in job and in political representation as well. This system was started by the founding fathers of the constitution for sixty years so that depressed classes of the society can get a fair chance of studies and can earn for a good living and for political representation as well. But the story is not same anymore. It is being extended for a period of ten years from time to time that today it has been amended to go on for 80 years after country is free. There could have been certain measures by which reservation could have benefitted people on ground reality and by the time it could have been eliminated from our country. The paper discusses on why reservation is provided and how it has been extended till date that it is around 60% today and what could be done now foreseeing today's scenario.

Background

Quota systems favouring certain caste and other communities existed before independence in several areas of British India. (Franco and Bulomine Regi.2016; Saxena et al,2015). The British has introduced elements of reservation in the government of India Act 1909 and there were many other measures put in place before independence. (Jangir 2013; Retna,2012) A significant one emerged from round table conference of June 1932, when, Prime Minister of Britain, Ramsay MacDonald proposed communal award which stated for separate representation on basis of community for Sikh, Muslims and Christians, Anglo Indians, Europeans, scheduled caste. This representation meant that people from a particular community will vote to the representative from that community only. It was opposed by Mahatma Gandhi that he started hunger strike, but this was favoured by Dr. BR Ambedkar and he tried to convince Gandhiji resulting into signing of Pune pact.

Reservations in favour of backward classes were introduced in a way before independence by a presidency area and princely states south of Vindhyas. If we consider 1881, Hunter commission came into limelight. Then, Mahatma Jyotiba Phule made a demand for free and compulsory education for Smrti with extra benefits for them in jobs. Looking forward to 1891, in the princely states of Travancore, there was a demand for reservation because nonnative people were been selected for public services overlooking qualified native people. Then, in princely state of Kolhapur, Maharashtra, it was introduced in 1901 in favour of non-Brahmin and backward classes. He provided free and accessible education to all. He worked for class free India and abolishing of untouchability. The notification of 1902 created 50% reservation in services for backward classes in State of Kolhapur. This is first official instance (Government Order,) providing for reservation for depressed class in India.

Objective of study The aim of the paper Reservation and Social Justice is to find out how the system of reservation came into existence. The condition of society is also seen on what situations were the people in, that they needed reservation and how reservation helped in gaining social justice. It also aimed at clarifying what is social justice and how is it maintained in democratic country like India, Measures provided for providing social justice to people. It is also maintained in the paper to have a solution on what social justice means to people and how it is a problem for some people in the society. The paper also talked of how the system of reservation can be removed from the society where we have number of people depending on this system for their jobs and education as well.

Review of Literature

While the Reservation System has received significant attention from policymakers and the Indian population over the years, there is still a dearth of academic literature analyzing it. Fundamentally, very few studies have chosen to ask the question of the Reservation Systems impact on poverty reduction and the results tend to be mixed. The economic diversity within the Scheduled groups makes this a complex study.

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The Constitution of India by D. D. basu has explained that Serves as an introductory study on the Constitution for general readers, politicians, journalists, statesmen, administrative authorities, students, and Public. Service Commission and other competitive examination aspirants. Traces the constitutional history of India since the Government of India Act, 1858, analyses the provisions of the present Constitution and explains the interrelation between its diverse contents Gives an account of the working of each of the provisions of the Constitution during its first decade, with reference to statutes and decisions wherever necessary, together with a critical estimate of its trends. Analytical table of contents, marginal notes, index, and reference tables further aid understanding. Contains all legislative changes and recent amendments to the Constitution up to the Constitution (One Hundred and Fourth Amendment) Act, 2019. Includes notable judgements of the Supreme Court and High Courts.

Main Text

After independence

The primary stated objective of Indian reservation system is to increase the opportunities for enhanced social and educational status of the underprivileged communities and to uplift their lifestyle to come up in mainstream of Indian society which is developing the reservation was provided to increase political representation in state and centre, school, colleges and other public institutions and for jobs as well. The government undertook several measures and policies to reserving a certain number of seats in public jobs and government-aided educational institutions for the SC and ST. The reservation quota in educational institutions and government jobs is 7.5% for the ST and 15% for the SC. The total reservation for both SC and ST stands at 22.5%. Reservation was further extended to the Other Backward Classes or OBCs in 1992 to 27%. Today 50% of reservation is allowed for the Sc, St, and OBCs in educational institutions and public jobs (Castelló-Climent & Mukhopadhyay, 2013) The period of reservation was extended to 1980,1990, 2000 and 2010 by 23rd, 45th, 62nd and 79th amendments, respectively. The 95 amendments extended the period of reservation to 2020. The period of reservation was further extended to 2030 by 104th amendment. Additionally, in 2019, the bill of reservation of 10% for economically weaker section in general category has been provided. This has resulted in total reservation counted to 60%.

Constitutional provisions

The Constitution provides several provisions related to reservation discussed below. Article 15(4) and 16(4) of the Constitution enabled both the state and Central Governments to reserve seats in public services for the members of the SC and ST, thereby, enshrining impartiality of opportunity in matters of civic service. Article 15(4) states that: "Nothing in this Article shall prevent the State from making any provision for the reservation of appointments or posts in favour of any backward class or citizens, which, in the opinion of the State, is not adequately represented in the services under the State.

"Article 16(4 A) states that: "Nothing in this article shall prevent the State from making any provisions for reservation in the matter of promotion to any class or classes of posts in the services under the State in Favor of SCs and STs which in the opinion of the State are not adequately represented under the State" (Constitutional 77th Amendment, - Act, 1995). Article 16 (4 B) states that: "Nothing in this article shall prevent the State from considering any unfilled vacancies of a year which are reserved for being filled up in that year in accordance with any provision for reservation made under clause (4) or clause (4A) as a separate class of vacancies to be filled up in any succeeding year or years and such class of vacancies shall not be considered together with the vacancies of the year in which they are being filled up for determining the ceiling of fifty percent reservation on total number of vacancies of that year" (Constitutional 81st Amendment, - Act, 2000).

The Constitution prohibits discrimination (Article 15) of any citizen on grounds of religion, race, caste, etc.; untouchability (Article 17); and forced labour (Article 23). It provides for specific representation through reservation of seats for the SCs and the STs in the Parliament (Article 330) and in the State Legislative Assemblies (Article 332), as well as, in Government and public sector jobs, in both the federal and state governments (Articles 16(4), 330(4) and 335). (Sukhadeo Thorat and Chittaranjan Senapati 2006).

The process of reservation is being extended on the grounds of article 334 which states:

1. Short title and commencement (1) This Act may be called the Constitution (Ninety- fifth Amendment) Act, 2009. (2) It shall come into force on the 25th day of January, 2010.

2. Amendment of article 334 In article 334 of the Constitution, for the words "sixty years", the words "seventy years" shall be substituted.[2] The full text of Article 334 of the Constitution, after the 95th Amendment, is given below: 368. Reservation of seats and special representation to cease after ten years. Notwithstanding anything in the foregoing provisions of this Part [Part XVI], the provisions of this Constitution relating to— (a) the reservation of seats for the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes in the House of the People and in the Legislative Assemblies of the States; and

(b) the representation of the Anglo-Indian community in the House of the People and in the Legislative Assemblies of the States by nomination shall cease to have effect on the expiration of a period of sixty years seventy years from the commencement of this Constitution: Provided that nothing in this article shall affect any representation in the House of the People or in the legislative Assembly of a State until the dissolution of the then existing House or Assembly, as the case may be.[3]

What could be done??

As Dr Ambedkar said, reservation policy must be so designed as to reconcile two conflicting interests, namely, there should be equality of opportunity for all citizens and there must, at the same time, be the provision made for the entry of certain communities, which have so far been outside the administration. Clause (1) of Article 16 guarantees that there shall be equality of opportunity for all citizens in matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the state. Clause (4) enables the state to make any provision for the reservation of appointments or post in favour of any Backward Class of citizens which, in opinion of the state, is not adequately represented in the services under the state. The objective of article 16(4) is empowerment of the deprived backward communities to give them a share in the administrative apparatus and in the governance of the community. The courts have interpreted the reservation of backward classes in such a way that will adjust protective discrimination to right to equal opportunity.

If we really want right to equality, even after considering upliftment of classes that need reservation, and providing all the people a ground of social justice, right to equality, right to equality of opportunity, then there is a need to look upon certain things like: - Reservation should not exceed half the vacancies to be filled at any time considering all types of reservations provided to different sections of society. As providing reservation for more than 50% will mock to the constitutional provision of right to equality. If so, this is simply power politics not social justice. - A big no to reservation on religion basis. Our country is secular and it needs to reflect that - The quota of reservation beginning with 50% should decrease year by year by 1%, which will result into zero reservation after long 50 years and a goal of egalitarian, democratic, casteless society will emerge in the meantime. - Reservations provided to the people should be revised and checked after looking different aspects and changing circumstances. - Caste should not be the only criteria for reservation. Rather, economic, land holding, property and the like things should also be kept in mind. - Reservation should only be provided on initial stages, not for further promotions. Reservations may help people to get a job once, then they need to work on their own for future benefits or promotions. It has always happened that whenever there is a point to remove or decrease reservation, people of that caste or community starts protesting and provide violent resistance for it. In such a situation, all the political parties need to be united as one for this purpose then only this may be checked. Here is a quote from a writer on reservation, power struggle and social justice. It's quoting social justice is not merely amelioration of the downtrodden and deprived section of the society.

Conclusion

It is certainly that but it must be done carefully and cautiously, cautiously in such a manner that it does not create more of downtrodden than it uplifts. Secondly, it is imperative that it is done in a manner that the quality of life (social, academic, scientific, material, moral) does not deteriorate. That will be detrimental to all to what may be called the haves as well as the have nots. Is it in the interest of the Dalits that scientific or academic or technological progress or economic development or social morality should come to the halt or should degenerate. If it is not, then the amelioration programme should be formulated and implemented with the willing consent and cooperation of all sections of people and not merely imposed in a manner that smacks of tyranny of the majority. It must be underlined, if standards moral or material decline, then everybody is a sufferer. A standard physician or surgeon will be risky to the patient, regardless of the latter's caste, community or religion. If the administrator lacks efficiency, honesty, sincerity, professional skills, it falls out affects everybody more so the weak and the poor than the well to do and the rich. So, there is general social interest in maintaining standards of morality, efficiency and scientific, technological and academic levels. This cannot be achieved without evolving rational restraint on the current political rat race for reservation.

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